

EFFECT OF ANTI-EPILEPTIC MEDICATIONS ON INTRAOPERATIVE 5-AMINOLEVULINIC ACID FLUORESCENCE DURING GLIOMA RESECTION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Background

Aminolevulinic acid (5-ALA) is a fluorescent dye that holds paramount importance in improving the extent of resection in glioma surgery. However, recent studies have shown that pre-operative administration of anti-epileptic medication (AEM) reduces the fluorescence of 5-ALA in gliomas. Since it is common for individuals with gliomas to require AEM, and 5-ALA is a far more cost-effective mechanism for providing enhanced intraoperative visualization compared to other means, it is crucial to determine if preoperative AEM administration is a factor that influences the visibility of 5-ALA.

Objectives

We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to analyze the impact of AEM on the intraoperative fluorescence of 5-ALA in patients with glioma.

Materials & Methods

We systematically reviewed four databases till 2022 to retrieve articles that met our inclusion criteria: 1) adult patients with glioma who underwent surgical resection using 5-ALA, 2) studies with both patients with preoperative AEM administration and without AEM administration, 3) Studies that report fluorescence intensity for both groups.

Results

Four observational studies, with a cumulative 344 patients, were included in the meta-analysis. 41.67% of our cohort were females, with the median age across the articles ranging from 33 to 66 years. 58.14% of patients had grade 4 gliomas, and 59.3% of gliomas were IDH1- wild type. Levetiracetam was the most administered AEM (73.17%). 47.8% were preoperatively given AEM, out of which 56.1% had visible fluorescence intraoperatively. Out of individuals who were not administered AEM, 82.7% had visible fluorescence. Our study found that the preoperative administration of AEM did not affect the visibility of intraoperative fluorescence [OR: 5.16 (0.27-99.99)].

Conclusions

Preoperative administration of AEM in patients with glioma has no impact on the degree of intraoperative fluorescence. We conclude that AEM can be utilized in glioma patients without incurring any risk of reduced visibility secondary to 5 ALA-induced fluorescence in intraoperative functional mapping.

Keywords: Aminolevulinic acid; Glioma; Intraoperative Fluorescence; Systematic Review

INTRODUCTION

Gliomas are intracranial tumors accounting for around 27% of all brain lesions and 80% of all malignant lesions in adults.^{1,2} The five-year survival rate for gliomas of all types is estimated to be around 35%; However, the 5-year survival rate drops to 10% in glioblastomas.¹ The survival rate depends on multiple factors; however, one of the most important predictors of survival in individuals with gliomas is the extent of resection (EOR). The 5-year survival rate for patients with glioblastoma who underwent gross total resection (GTR) is 30%, whereas individuals who underwent subtotal resection (STR) had a 5-year survival rate of 5.5%.³ In addition, individuals with low-grade gliomas undergoing GTR have a 5-year survival rate of 81%, almost twice that of individuals undergoing STR (44%).⁴

5-aminolevulinic acid (5-ALA) has been established as a highly effective fluorescent dye for fluorescence-guided surgery (FGS) of brain tumors. This technique relies on neoplastic cells' preferential uptake and subsequent metabolism of 5-ALA, resulting in the generation of protoporphyrin IX (PpIX), which emits red fluorescence when excited by blue light.⁵ The ability of 5-ALA to selectively label tumor cells enables precise intraoperative tumor visualization, facilitating the identification of tumor margins and enhancing the surgeon's ability to assess the dynamic changes occurring within the brain during the surgical intervention.⁶ In addition to improving intraoperative visualization, 5-ALA has been shown to minimize the degree of brain shift that occurs during surgery by enabling precise identification of the tumor borders allowing maximal safe resection while minimizing unnecessary resection of the surrounding tissue; hence it also aids in preserving neurological function.⁷

However, multiple in vitro and in vivo studies have recently shown that preoperative anti-epileptic medication (AEM) administration can lead to reduced intraoperative fluorescence of 5-ALA. It is not uncommon for patients with a brain tumor to

be administered AEM preoperatively, as seizures are one of the most common clinical manifestations of gliomas. Seizures are reported in around 40-60% patients with brain tumors.⁸ In such patients, administration of AEM is crucial, especially for intraoperative seizure control.

Hence, this systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted to determine whether the AEM administration preoperatively impacts the visibility of 5-ALA intraoperatively.

Methodology

This systematic review was carried out according to the procedures outlined in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement.

Search Strategy and Screening

A comprehensive search of the following databases was conducted: Medline, Cochrane, Embase, Scopus, and Web of Science. The medical literature on the above databases was performed from inception to the 9th of October 2023. A search strategy was constructed with the following keywords: "anticonvulsant," "antiepileptic," "levetiracetam," "phenytoin," "5-aminolevulinic acid," and "5-ALA". There were no limitations on the language of the study. To guarantee that all pertinent research was included, reference lists of screened papers were also scrutinized.

Data Extraction, Inclusion/ Exclusion Criteria

Two authors (AA and KN) screened the studies independently, while a third author (SAK) was consulted when any disagreements were encountered. Our inclusion includes:

1. Adult patients with glioma undergoing surgical resection using 5-ALA,
2. Studies with groups of patients who were preoperatively administered AED and patients who were not administered AED,
3. Studies that report intraoperative fluorescence visibility for groups with AED

administration and without AED administration.

Studies that were in vitro in nature were excluded, as well as studies not assessing fluorescence with respect to preoperative AED administration.

During the data extraction process, data on the author's names, publication date, country of origin, percentage of females in each study, median age, glioma grade, histopathology, types, and frequency of AED administered, visibility and intensity of 5-ALA in both groups.

Statistical Analysis

The risk of bias for the included studies was assessed using the assessment tool for observational studies created by the National Heart, Lung, and Brain Institute (NHLBI). The data analysis was

performed using Microsoft Excel and the software R. Descriptive data were presented as frequency/percentages, while continuous data will be reported as the median and interquartile range. Forest plots were used to determine the effect of AED on fluorescence visualization. Confidence intervals were calculated, and a P-value <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

A total of 49 studies were found eligible for title and abstract screening, and 39 were assessed for full-text eligibility. Only 4 observational studies met our inclusion criteria and were included in this systematic review and meta-analysis.⁹⁻¹² Figure 1 is a PRISMA flow diagram with information regarding the screening process.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram

This study included a total of 344 patients with glioma. Out of which, 41.67% of our cohort were females, with the median age across the articles ranging from 33 to 66 years. All the patients

included in the study are from high-income countries. Characteristics of the studies included in this review can be found in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Demographic features of the studies

Study	Country	Study design	Sample size	Female %	Age (median)	Age (IQR)
Johannes Wach et al. ¹⁰	Germany	Retrospective	175	37.70%	66.0	56-73
Lisa I.Wadiura et al. ¹¹	Austria and USA	Ambi-directional	110	47.20%	43.7	20-77
Sergey A. Goryaynov, et al. ⁹	Russia	Retrospective	27	42.10%	33.0	18-36
Kazuhide Shimizu et al. ¹²	Japan	Prospective	32	43.80%	53.0	23-81

The most common glioma grade in this study was grade 4, comprising 63.1% of cases that had reported the tumor grade in this study. Out of 237 cases that reported IDH1 status, 86.1% of the cases were IDH1-wildtype, and only 13.9% of the gliomas were IDH1-mutant type. Tumors located in the frontal lobe were most common in this study, comprising 46.2% of 132 individuals that reported the location of the glioma. Gliomas originating in the thalamus were the least common

location (0.75%). Glioblastomas comprised 197 of 265 cases, the most common type of glioma in this study. 18.5% of the gliomas were astrocytoma, out of which 18 were diffuse astrocytoma, 10 were anaplastic astrocytoma, 4 were pilocytic astrocytoma, and 2 were gemistocytic astrocytoma. Oligodendroglioma and desmoplastic infantile ganglioglioma were only 6.8% and 0.4%, respectively. 4.34% (9/207) of gliomas were recurrent tumors.

Table 2: features of glioma included in the study

Features of glioma in the population		Frequency (percentage)
Grades	4	200/317 (63.1%)
	3	48/317 (15.1%)
	2	69/317 (21.8%)
IDH1-status	IDH1-mutant	33/237 (13.9%)
	IDH1-wildtype	204/237 (86.1%)
Location of tumor	Frontal	61/132 (46.2%)
	Temporal	41/132 (32.1%)
	Parietal	12/132 (9.1%)
	Insular	17/132 (12.9%)
	Central	13/132 (9.8%)
	Thalamus	1/132 (0.75%)
Type of tumor	Glioblastoma	197/265 (74.3%)
	Astrocytoma	49/265 (18.5%)
	Oligodendroglioma	18/265 (6.8%)
	Desmoplastic infantile ganglioglioma	1/265 (0.4%)

164 patients were given AED pre-operatively (47.7%). However, information regarding which

anti-epileptics were used was available for only 149 patients. Out of which, 120 patients were given

levetiracetam (80.5%), 109/120 (90.8%) patients were given only levetiracetam, and 11/120 (9.2%) patients in addition to levetiracetam were given other anti-epileptics like Lacosamide, Lamotrigine Carbamazepine, Clobazam, Oxcarbazepine, Valproic acid, Lacosamide and Carbamazepine,

Clobazam and Carbamazepine, Valproic acid with Lacosamide and Mirtazapine. The studies that reported the AED used in their studies had a total of 4 (2.7%) patients for whom the AED was not known.

Table 3: Anti-epileptic drugs used preoperatively

Anti-epileptic drug	Frequency (N=149)
Levetiracetam alone	109 (73.2%)
Lamotrigine	7 (4.7%)
Valproate	5 (3.4%)
Carbamazepine	7 (4.7%)
Bupropion	1 (0.67%)
Oxcarbazepine	4 (2.7%)
Phenytoin	4 (2.7%)
Benzodiazepine	2 (1.3%)
Lacosamide	2 (1.3%)
Lacosamide + Carbamazepine	1 (0.67%)
Clobazam + Carbamazepine	1 (0.67%)
Valproic acid + Lacosamide + Mirtazapine	1 (0.67%)
Carbamazepine + Clonazepam	1 (0.67%)
Unknown	4 (2.7%)

Table 4 shows the intraoperative fluorescence status of patients with and without AED administration. Our study found that the preoperative administration of AEM did not affect the visibility of intraoperative fluorescence [OR: 5.16 (0.27- 99.99)] (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Forest plot comparing the AED and non-AED groups on the absence of intraoperative fluorescence during tumour resection

Table 4: Fluorescence status in pre-operative AED administration and without AED administration

AED administration	Total	Frequency (percentage)
Yes		164
Visible fluorescence		92 (56.1%)

No	No fluorescence	72 (43.9%)
	Total	179
	Visible fluorescence	148 (82.7%)
	No fluorescence	31 (17.3%)

Publication bias for comparison of AED and non-AED groups on the absence of intraoperative fluorescence during tumor resection was assessed using a funnel plot, shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Funnel plot to assess publication bias for comparison of AED and non-AED groups on the absence of intraoperative fluorescence during tumor resection.

Discussion

In 1993, Walter Stummer was the first to describe using 5-aminolevulinic acid in fluorescent-guided glioma surgery. Since then, 5-ALA has been widely used in surgeries for glioma resection as FGS with 5-ALA offers surgeons intraoperative visualization of tumor margins that aids in precise resection of the tumor, which helps achieve GTR in a higher percentage of patients and reduces the brain shift during surgery.

5-ALA is a compound that normally exists in our body and is pivotal in heme biosynthesis. Gliomas, especially high-grade gliomas, have an increased demand for heme biosynthesis, in addition to the greater degree of the disrupted blood-brain barrier; hence, the uptake of 5-ALA is substantially more in gliomas compared to normal tissues. 5-ALA, when administered, is readily taken up and metabolized into an endogenous photosensitizer called

protoporphyrin IX (PpIX). PpIX is the compound responsible for the red fluoresce visualized intraoperatively under a light with a 375-440nm wavelength.

However, some studies have reported that preoperative administration of AED reduces the amount of PpIX formed or the visibility of the fluorescence. A study done by Hefti et al. in 2012 showed that malignant glioma cell lines exposed to phenytoin showed reduced PpIX accumulation; however, in the same study, no difference was noted in the PpIX accumulation when the cell lines were exposed to levetiracetam.¹³ In addition, a study by Goryaynov et al. in 2019 showed reduced fluorescence in patients who were administered AED.⁹ Another study in 2022 showed significantly reduced fluorescence intraoperatively in patients who were preoperatively given levetiracetam.¹⁰ However, a study done in 2020 found no

difference in the intraoperative fluorescence of 5-ALA in the AED and non-AED groups.¹¹ After pooling the data from these studies, our meta-analysis concluded that AEDs do not influence the visibility of 5-ALA intraoperatively.

Nevertheless, the dosage of the AEDs administered was unavailable for most patients, which could've contributed to the varying findings across the studies included. Even though most of the patients in our study were given levetiracetam (73.2%), a variety of AEDs was still used in our population with different mechanisms of action. This is worth noting as some and not all AEDs may affect intraoperative fluorescence. The tumor's grade could influence the results as gliomas with higher grades have an increased heme biosynthesis; hence, they pick up the dye more readily compared to LGGs. Therefore, despite the negative influence of AED on fluorescence in HGGs, the intraoperative fluorescence of 5-ALA is still visible due to greater uptake than LGGs. Wadiura et al. reported that a greater percentage of patients with grade 3 and above gliomas had visible fluorescence than those below grade 3.¹¹ This study's limitation includes not being able to analyze if factors like the grade of glioma, dosage of AEDs, type of AED and IDH mutations affect the visibility and intensity of fluorescence. In addition, the studies included in this analysis employed different grading systems for the intensity of intraoperative fluorescence, due to which the authors of this study were unable to analyze if AEDs affect the intensity of the fluorescence.

5-ALA is a comparatively cheaper modality to achieve GTR while limiting neurological deficits. Hence it is extremely valuable to neurosurgeons working in LMICs, despite all recent advancements that improve intraoperative visualization. In addition, a meta-analysis by Golub et al. performed in 2020 found no significant difference between the percentage of patients in which GTR was achieved in cases where 5-ALA was used compared to cases where an intraoperative MRI was used.¹⁴ However, despite the abovementioned literature, a literature review 2020 suggested that there is data available to suggest interactions between the metabolic pathways of phenytoin, levetiracetam and 5-ALA at a cellular level, whether that translates to produce a clinical effect is still not established.¹⁵ We understand 5-ALA is extremely valuable and makes it crucial to understand the factors that alter the visibility and intensity of

fluorescence of 5-ALA. Hence, further prospective studies are required to understand if dosage, frequency, and type of AED truly influence the intraoperative visibility and intensity of 5-ALA.

Conclusion

Preoperative administration of AEM in patients with glioma has no impact on the degree of intraoperative fluorescence. We conclude that AEM can be utilized in glioma patients without incurring any risk of reduced visibility secondary to 5-ALA-induced fluorescence during intraoperative resection.

Abbreviations list

Aminolevulinic acid (5-ALA)
Anti-epileptic medication (AEM)
Gross total resection (GTR)
Subtotal resection (STR)
Extent of resection (EOR)
Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)
National Heart, Lung, and Brain Institute (NHLBI).

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